

THE AGRICULTUREME "LOCALITY" AS A REPRESENTATION OF LINGUISTICS AND CULTURE IN THE TOPONYMY OF ENGLAND AND THE USA

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Abstract. The article compares the agricultureme "locality" in England and the USA. In both the USA and England, agriculture plays a significant role in shaping the linguistic and cultural aspects of localities. This is reflected in the use of place names that indicate agricultural heritage. Village names in England often reference farms or fields, highlighting the historical importance of farming in these areas. Similarly, town and county names in the USA may incorporate references to specific crops grown in those regions, emphasizing the agricultural focus. Even in urban areas, street names can commemorate the agricultural past, serving as reminders of the historical connection between agriculture and the development of the locality. These representations of agriculture in toponymy reflect the identity and history of these regions, signifying the importance of agriculture in shaping local culture, economy, and way of life. All these elements contribute to the overall representation of agriculture as a key aspect of linguistic and cultural identity in both the USA and England.

Keywords: agricultural heritage, place names, farming, village names, town names, county names, crops, street names, identity, history, culture, economy, way of life, toponymy, linguistic and cultural identity.

Agriculture plays a significant role in shaping the linguistic and cultural aspects of localities in both the USA and England. This is evident in the use of place names that reference agricultural heritage, highlighting the historical importance of farming in these areas. Village names in England often allude to farms or fields, while town and county names in the USA may incorporate references to specific crops grown in those regions. Even in urban areas, street names can serve as reminders of the historical connection between agriculture and the development of the locality [2, 95-116].

These representations of agriculture in toponymy reflect the identity and history of these regions, signifying the importance of agriculture in shaping local culture, economy, and way of life. They serve as a constant reminder of the agricultural heritage and its impact on the community. However, it is important to note that there are many other ways in which agricultural heritage can be represented, such as through festivals, traditions, local cuisine, or the presence of agricultural museums or landmarks.

The representation of the agricultural theme "locality" in toponymy, or place names, varies between England and the USA. In England, village names often reflect their agricultural heritage, with names like "Farmington" or "Fieldgate" indicating the presence of farms or fields in the area. These names highlight the agricultural activities associated with specific locations [5, 685-695].

Similarly, in the USA, town names may incorporate agricultural references to highlight their farming history. Examples include names like "Cornville" or "Wheatland," which signify the predominant crops grown in those areas. County names in some states also pay homage to agriculture, with names like "Cotton County" or "Peach County" emphasizing the significance of cotton or peach farming in those regions. Even in urban areas, street names may

commemorate the agricultural past of the locality, with names like "Harvest Lane" or "Orchard Street" referencing previous farmland [4, 16].

Moreover, the use of agricultural terms in toponymy creates a sense of place and helps people connect with their surroundings. It fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation for the land, its history, and the people who have shaped it through their agricultural practices. These toponyms serve as a bridge between past and present, reminding us of the importance of agriculture in our societies [3, 14-24].

All these elements contribute to the overall representation of agriculture as a key aspect of linguistic and cultural identity in both the USA and England. The toponymy of these regions serves as a testament to the historical and ongoing significance of agriculture in shaping local communities and their way of life.

In conclusion, agriculture's influence on toponymy in the USA and England is a testament to the significance of farming in shaping linguistics and culture. These agricultural toponyms not only provide valuable insights into the historical and geographical aspects of these regions but also contribute to their cultural identity. They serve as reminders of the hard work, traditions, and heritage associated with agriculture, connecting people to the land and its rich history.

References:

1. Clark, C. 'Onomastics', in *The Cambridge History of the English Language II: 1066-1476*, ed. N.Blake (Cambridge, 1992), pp. 542-606
2. Helleland B. 2012. Place names and identities. In: B Helleland, CE Ore & S Wikstrom (eds). *Names and identities. Oslo Studies in Language*, 4(2):95-116
3. Khvesko T. V. (2018). Place names metaphora in language and communication. *Language and Culture*, (12), 14-24.
4. Leonovich O.A. "Toponyms of California: (Linguistic analysis of the names of populated areas): The author of the dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. (10.66.3) / O.A. Leonovich; Moscow State Pedagogical University of Foreign Languages named after M. Torez. - M., 1972. - 16с.
5. Yuryeva Julia B. (2018). Honorific titles in British English and American English. *Вестник Российского университета дружбы народов. Серия: Теория языка. Семиотика. Семантика*, 9 (3), 685-695.